

EMPIRICAL LEVEL OF SCIENTIFIC KNOWLEDGE

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Annotation. *In the structure of scientific knowledge, first of all, there are two levels of knowledge - empirical and theoretical. They correspond to two interrelated, but at the same time specific types of cognitive activity: empirical and theoretical research. Empirical and theoretical are philosophical and general scientific categories that describe the main forms and levels of scientific research. The empirical degree is the knowledge gained as a result of experience and associated with the processing of the properties and relations of the object in question.*

Key words: *empirical, figurative thinking, rational, scientific category, object, abstract, philosophical, principle, analysis, synthesis.*

The empirical level of cognition is knowledge obtained directly from experience and associated with the processing of the properties and relations of the object under study. It always provides a level of theoretical knowledge. Theoretical is knowledge obtained through a stepwise system of thinking. At the empirical level, figurative thinking (emotional cognition) predominates; rational method and its forms have the following meaning. Therefore, the object under study is mainly reflected in its external relations and phenomena, it is convenient for thinking and expresses internal relations.

Empirical research is directed directly (without intermediate connections) to its object. Using such techniques and means as comparison, observation, measurement, experimentation, he processes the object in artificially created and controlled conditions (including mental ones), assimilates it through analysis, induction, etc.

The theoretical level of scientific knowledge is characterized by the superiority of the rational moment and its forms (concepts, laws and other aspects of thinking). Theoretical knowledge reflects events and processes from the point of view of their internal connections, understood through rational processing of empirical cognitive data. This processing is carried out with the help of abstract systems of a "higher order" - concepts, conclusions, laws, categories, principles, etc.

Empirical and theoretical levels of knowledge differ in the subject, means and methods of research. In fact, these two layers of knowledge constantly interact and are organically linked. Their interaction is based on the practice of expanding all aspects

and levels of cognitive activity, combining its various aspects as a result of new knowledge.

The generally accepted classifications of empirical and theoretical methods of scientific knowledge are given in Table. 1.

The growing role of science in social development, its penetration into all spheres of people's lives, the quality of training of future specialists depend on the direction of research in the educational process. An important aspect of it is the formation of research skills in a future specialist, which necessitates the formation of an approach to life, profession, and self-knowledge among students.

Methods of scientific knowledge

Table. 1.

Empiricist	Theoretical
<p>Observation – is a purposeful and organized perception of objects and phenomena related to the solution of a specific scientific problem.</p> <p>An experiment – is a method of scientific knowledge in which real events are investigated under controlled and controlled conditions.</p>	<p>Analysis – is the division of the object of study into its component parts.</p> <p>The combination of elements obtained as a result of synthesis-analysis.</p> <p>Comparison is the determination of the similarity or difference of objects.</p> <p>Abstraction – is a mental separation of the main properties of the observed object.</p> <p>Modeling (as an activity and result) is a mental or material system that reflects the object of study.</p> <p>Induction – is an individual output.</p> <p>Deduction – is the transition from the general to the particular.</p> <p>Analogy – is a method of comparing knowledge about one object with another.</p>

From the point of view of our study, the analysis of the experience of higher educational institutions allowed us to draw the following conclusions: the complication and mastery of new types of educational activities is a key element of the educational process, which determines the personal growth of the future professional, his formation as a specialist;

- to prepare a student for research activities, professional and personal qualities are necessary, which are formed in the process of integrated learning;
- the system of research skills determines the self-education of the personal qualities of a specialist, necessary for effective professional activity.

The formation of research qualities plays a leading role in the overall process of professional training of a future specialist, and their adequate self-assessment determines the professional orientation and competence of the individual. The first one consists of the following motives: purpose, understanding the value of the profession, the need for high-quality professional training, interest in research activities. Professional competence implies the consistency of professional knowledge and skills, methodological knowledge as the basis of scientific training and a set of research skills.

Let's look at the definition of "ability". In the psychological and pedagogical literature there is no uniform interpretation of it. The pedagogical encyclopedia contains the concept of "ability" given by E.N.Kabanova-Meller: ability is described as "performing an action (activity) in accordance with the conditions under which it is necessary to act" [1]. M.A.Danilov and B.P.Esipov define abilities in the pedagogical dictionary as "readiness for practical and theoretical actions that must be performed quickly, accurately and consciously on the basis of acquired knowledge and life experience" [1].

In the pedagogical dictionary, the concept of "skill" is defined as "an action characterized by a high level of skill, at the stage of which the action becomes automated" [2].

Ya.Zimnaya believes that skill is "a set of actions leading to perfection as a result of repeated purposeful exercises" [3].

The foregoing clearly articulates conflicting views on various aspects of the problem of skills and competencies that exist in science. We agree with the views of the authors who studied the concepts of "ability" and "skill", showing their commonality. The commonality of skills and competencies lies in the fact that they include both conscious and subconscious components and play a certain role in human activity. The difference between abilities and skills lies in the suitability of the skill for a conscious purpose.

Thus, the ability can be understood as the ability to effectively perform a certain activity in accordance with the goals and conditions of its implementation.

Skill (in our understanding) is a method of action (operation) characterized by a high level of skill.

The research skills discussed in our study are related to teaching skills. In pedagogy, pedagogical skills are grouped into two main groups: special and general education.

The skills of special training are formed within the framework of one academic discipline, and the skills of general professional training are formed in the system of most academic disciplines. Our study and analysis of the literature makes it possible to emphasize that the research skills formed in students in the process of teaching general education subjects are general educational skills.

Ability - the readiness of the individual for specific actions or processes in accordance with the goals set on the basis of existing knowledge and the conditions for its implementation (Yu.K.Babansky [11], M.A.Danilov [39], B.P.Esipov [41], V. A.Slastenin [127], A.V.Usova [140], N. M.Yakovlev [158]).

Before considering the issues of effective organization of teaching students of engineering specialties in general education subjects, it is necessary to highlight the basic concepts that describe the process of developing research skills.

Different encyclopedic dictionaries give two definitions of the concept of "education". In the dictionary of S.I.Ozhegov, "education is 1) giving completeness to a certain form; 2) creation, organization [96, p. 844]. Development is understood as "the process of transition from one state to another, the transition from the old to the new" [9]. In our study, we found that these two processes run in parallel to each other.

Scientific research is the process of mastering new scientific knowledge, which is one of the types of cognitive activity. Scientific research is characterized by objectivity, reproducibility, evidence, accuracy (understood differently in different fields of science) [2].

In the psychological and pedagogical dictionary, "research" is described as the result of scientific activity aimed at obtaining socially significant new knowledge about the structure of pedagogical processes and patterns, the mechanism of education, theory and history of pedagogy, methods of organizing education, its content, principles, methods, organizational forms. The method of research in teaching is a method of involving students in independent and direct observations, on the basis of which connections between objects and phenomena are established, conclusions are drawn. The inclusion of elements of research in teaching contributes to educating students in activity, initiative, curiosity, and develops their thinking [9].

The principle of research activity involves the organization of such an educational process in which students get acquainted with new research methods used in the disciplines they study, master the existing elements of the research methodology, independently acquire new knowledge by studying natural and social phenomena.

The application of the principle of research contributes to the development of cognitive abilities, increases interest in mastering scientific knowledge and methods of scientific and cognitive activity. The advantage of the research principle in teaching is that the teacher can direct students to selectively study the subject necessary for the formation of their research skills [101].

I.Ya.Lerner and M. N. Skatkin emphasize that the research method, which has long been used in pedagogical practice, is necessary for the simultaneous assimilation of creative activity, knowledge and skills” [6]. a way of organizing the research, creative activity of students by decision” [6].

M.I.Makhmutov believes that the research method of teaching (training) is one of the most effective ways of organizing problem-based learning, providing a high level of knowledge of students, independent activity” [7].

The research method "provides the mastery of scientific methods of cognition, forms the characteristics of creative activity, provides quick and flexible cognition" [9]. The research method of P.I. Pidkasist "is designed to ensure the creative application of knowledge. Students master the methods of scientific knowledge, the experience of their research activities is formed" [9].

In her dissertation research, T.N.Shipilova [155] argues that research skills are “the ability to conduct scientific and empirical research in various fields. Empirical research ensures the effectiveness of the formation of research skills through the use of invariants of educational activity.

V.V.Uspensky considers research ability as "the ability to make independent observations, experiments obtained in the process of solving research problems" [0]. The author also claims that “the ability of a researcher is the ability to compare, analyze, distinguish, generalize, highlight important features” [4].

Pedagogical research ability was studied in detail by N.M. Yakovlev. The author characterizes them as “observation and analysis of pedagogical phenomena (facts) from dialectical materialistic approaches and the formation and solution of pedagogical tasks on this basis: hypothesis; development and implementation of the experiment; processing and summarizing the results of the experiment; implementation, use of achievements in the field of pedagogy” [5].

S.P.Arsenov defines research ability as a conscious ability of a set of processes that are ways to perform mental or applied research actions (organization of research activities), the formation and success of their formation depend on previously acquired skills and abilities [9].

P.Yu.Romanov gives the following definition of research ability: “research ability is the ability of a student to effectively perform actions corresponding to the content of each level of the educational system, to solve a problem in accordance with the logic of scientific research. based on existing knowledge and skills” [8].

After analyzing these definitions and relevant studies, we note that research skills have a specific content. They consist of individual terms formed on the basis of relevant knowledge and skills. The views of scientists on the structure of research ability are very diverse in terms of 1) highlighting certain abilities as part of research ability and 2) analyzing various classifications.

Yu.K.Babansky analyzes the organization of educational activities, determines its content and divides research abilities into three groups: 1) the ability to choose goals; 2) the ability to choose your own path; 3) the ability to apply the acquired knowledge in the practical implementation of the study [12].

Many authors note that research activity by its nature is divided into theoretical and empirical. In the process of theoretical research, hypotheses or principles are put forward, and the theory is used to explain and predict events. In the course of empirical research, cognitive efforts are made to comprehend the results of practical activities, observations and experiments to collect empirical data [144].

Empirical object - these are properties, connections, relations of phenomena found in the process of practical activity, observations, experiments. A characteristic feature of an empirical object is its existence for sensory perception" [4].

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